

A Study of Socio- Economic Status of Workforce of Kalichabad Village of Jaunpur Tehsil, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

It has been observed that socio- economic condition of the people working in unorganized sector of Kalichabad village of Jaunpur Tehsil is far graver than what the successive governments of Uttar Pradesh have projected. The population has low literacy rate, deep rooted caste system, religious affiliations, superstitions etc have been found to be strongly existing there and this has been exploited by the political parties over the years for their own gains. Workers are mostly the part of unorganized sector engaged in jobs like agriculture and allied activities, welding, plumbing, small trading, shop keeping etc. and face the problems such as low earnings, health hazards, lack of access to basic amenities like accommodation, drinking water, toilets, poor education etc. In this study, author attempts to identify the occupational status of the respondents, their socio -economic status, and gives certain suggestions which should be adhered to by the local and state public authorities for their upliftment. The research design used in this study is exploratory cum analytical. It is exploratory because the study is the first of its kind done on workers of Kalichabad where the researcher has made an attempt to explore the socio-economic problems and find out the solutions to these problems. At the same time, it is analytical because after finding out the facts through empirical data, researcher has done the analysis on the basis of which inferences have been drawn and recommendations have been put forth.

Key words: Illiteracy, Income and Employment, Infrastructure, Transport, Warehouses

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the income, nature of employment of the people of Kalichabad.
2. To find out and analyse the living standards of the respondents.
3. To explore the problems which the workforce has been facing in production and distribution process.
4. To give recommendations on the basis of inferences drawn about how to address the identified problems.

Research Methodology and Tool of Data Collection

The data for the present study was obtained from two sources namely primary sources (data collected from the respondents by using an interview schedule) and secondary sources (data collected from books, newspapers, and websites, journals and resource persons). A total of 65 respondents were selected for the purposive sampling and pre-tested interview schedule. The tool of data collection used for the study was an interview schedule. The interview schedule was prepared keeping in view the low literacy level of the likely respondents, their convenience and time availability. The interview schedule consisted of personal data, working and living conditions, willingness to cooperate with the researcher etc.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

Some of the major short comings of this study is that only those respondents who were available and willing to cooperate were chosen for the study.

Among the workforce, people engaged in agricultural work, shop keeping, welding, plumbing, milk business and tailoring were selected for the study. But many other workers engaged in jobs like broom making, flour milling, vendors and hawkers selling small daily utility products, handicrafts etc were not included in the study due to their non-willingness to provide the needed data as well as paucity of time.

Back ground

Kalichabad village is located in Jaunpur Tehsil of Jaunpur district in Uttar Pradesh. As per 2011 census, it has a population of 5614 people out of which 2844 are male and 2770 are female. Majority population is rural based and is engaged in agriculture, allied and small activities like plumbing, tailoring, welding, small trading etc. In order to find out and analyse the socio-economic status of this section of workforce of this village, researcher has based the study on criteria like age group, literacy rate, nature of occupation, income level, living standards, availability or lack of basic amenities, infrastructure facilities for production and distribution etc. Accordingly, the questions for interview were prepared to obtain the data.

Findings and Inferences Total Number of Respondents 65

Table No: 1 Age Wise Distribution of the Respondents.

S.No	Age	Number	Percentage
1	15-25	14	21.5
2	26-35	16	24.61
3	36-45	12	18.4
4	45-55	12	18.4
5	56 and above	11	16.9
6	Total	65	100

The above shows that 21.5 per cent respondents were 15-25 years old and 24.61 per cent respondents were 26-35 years old. 18.4 per cent

respondents were 36-45 and 45-55 years old and 16.9 per cent respondents were 56 and above.

Table No. 2 Literacy Level of Respondents.

S.No	Literacy level	Number	Percentage
1	Illiterate	27	41.5
2	Elementary education	18	27.69
3	Secondary	11	16.9
4	High school	8	12.3
5	Intermediate	1	1.5
6	Graduation	Nil	Nil
	Total	65	100

Table 2 shows literacy level of the workers. 41.5 per cent respondents were illiterate; 27.6 per cent respondents had elementary education, 16.9 per cent had secondary level of education, 12.3 per cent respondents had high school level of education, 1.5 per cent respondents were educated up to

intermediate. It is noteworthy to see that no one was graduate. Due to poverty their parents didn't send them to schools and likewise they too don't send their children to school and encourage their children to help them in their occupation.

Table. No.3. Nature of Employment of Respondents

S.No	Occupation	Number	Percentage
1	Agriculture Labour	16	24.6
2	Milk Business and chilly cutting	12	18.4
3	Shop keeping (Agarbatti, matchboxes, candles, plastic ware etc) and Agriculture	10	15.3
4	Tailoring	8	12.3
5	Plumbing	11	16.9
6	Welding	8	12.3
	Total	65	100

The above table shows that 24.6 per cent respondents were mainly engaged in agriculture work, while 15.3 percent did shop keeping along with agriculture labour. 18.4 percent were engaged in milk business as main and chilly cutting as aside business, whereas 12.3 percent were engaged in tailoring and welding work each. 16.9% of respondents were engaged in Plumbing work. However, people who are engaged in agriculture

have to frequently switch over to other jobs when crop season is over. Hence their socio-economic conditions are not satisfactory as its very difficult for them to find alternative source of employment during lean season.

Table. No.4. Gross Annual Income of Respondents.

S.No	Yearly income	Number	Percentage
1	25000-50000	30	46.1
2	50 thousand-1 lakh	14	21.5
3	1 Lakh-1.5 lakh	10	15.3
4	1.5 Lakh- 2lakh	9	13.8
5	2 lakh and above	2	3.07
	Total	65	100

Table 4 shows annual gross income of respondents. 46.1% respondents were between 25 thousand to 50 thousand, 21.2% were earning between 50 thousand to -1 lakh 15.3% respondents were in income group of 1 lakh to 1.5 lakh ,13.8 were earning between 1.5

lakh to 2 lakh whereas 3.07% were earning 2 lakh and above. This proves that majority of respondents earned between five to eight thousand per month which cannot be termed as decent money in present types with prevailing inflation rates.

Table. No.5. Living Standards of Respondents

S.No.	Modern Gadgets and Appliances Used	Number	Percentage
1	Cooker	13	20
2	Cooking Gas	9	13.8
3	Iron	8	12.3
4	T.V.	4	6.1
5	Mobile Phones	8	12.3
6	Sewing Machines	7	10.7
7	Fans	5	7.6
8	Motor cycles	1	1.5
9	Bicycle	3	4.6
10	None	7	10.7
	Total	65	100

The above table gives clear idea about the living standards of the respondents which has been evaluated in terms of the gadgets used in their daily routine .20% were using cooker,13.8% were using cooking gas, and 12.3% used iron. The table clearly

shows that gadgets like T.V, fans, sewing machines were used by very less percentage of respondents. Hardly 4.6% could afford to use bicycle and 1.5% had motorcycle. 10.7% are so poor that they cannot afford any of the gadget in their day to day lives.

Table No.6 Nature of Accommodation of Respondents.

S. No	Nature of accommodation	Number	Percentage
1	Kuccha houses made of mud, ropes and plastics	13	20
2	Semi pucca houses of mud and bricks	29	44.6
3	Pucca houses	15	23.07
4	Temporary houses (tents or tambu)	8	12.3
	Total	65	100

The above table shows the type of dwellings respondents live in. While 20% live in kuccha houses, 44.6% have their houses made of bricks and mud,23.07% have cemented pucca houses and

12.3% live in tents. This proves the housing scene of the respondents is very pathetic. Government claims that 75% people have been provided with pucca dwellings proves to be wrong here.

Table No. 7 Availability of Source of Usable Water by Respondents.

S.No	Usable Water Source	Number	Percentage
1	Tap water	6	9.2
2	Tube wells	11	16.9
3	Hand pumps	35	53.8
4	Well	9	13.8
5	Pond	4	6.15
	Total	65	100

The above table gives tells that 9.2% of respondents have access to tap water, 16.9% get water from tube wells, 53.8% draw water from handpumps and 13.8% from wells.6.15% have to use pond water for drinking and cooking. Hence it is observed that even

today significant percentage of people in this village do not have access to clean usable water and have to rely on unclean water from ponds, wells etc leading to health hazards

Table No. 8 Type of Toilets used by Respondents.

S.No.	Type of Toilets	Number	Percentage
1	Indian toilet	28	43.07
2	Make Shift(temporary)	20	30.7
3	Modern	Nil	nil
4	None	17	26.1
	Total	65	100

Table 8 indicates the grave scenario of hygiene and toilet facilities of the respondents. Only 43.07% have access to Indian toilets, while 26.1% have no toilet facility at all and have to defecate in

open.30.7% of respondents use make shift toilets which are purely temporary in nature. Not a single respondent knew about the modern concept of toilet.

Table No. 9 Infra Structural Problems faced by the Respondents in the Process of Production and Supply (Sales and Marketing).

S. No	Problems	Number	Percentage
1	Warehousing and godown and Transport	25	38.6
2	Inadequate Transport	17	26.1
3	Shortage of raw materials	10	15.3
4	Shortage of electricity and power	13	20
	Total	65	100

Table 9 shows that 38.6 per cent respondents complained about inadequate godown and warehousing facility along with transport facility, 26.1 per cent respondents faced the problem of inadequate transport facility due to which they were not able to get supplies of raw materials, tools and equipment, needed to do the production and unable to carry their produce to the markets and mandis for sale. 15.3% faced the problem of irregular supply of raw materials and 20 per cent respondents were facing problems of shortage of electricity and power. All these have led to these workers facing serious problems in production and distribution of their produce in the market.

Recommendations

1. On the basis of the findings the author gives certain recommendations some of which are specified below:
2. Since the income level of the respondents is very low, it is the need of the hour that government should provide financial aid through welfare schemes so as to ensure that the people of this village are able to get decent earning from their jobs and are also able to get alternative source of employment in case they have to switch over from their present work due to certain reasons.
3. Since literacy rates among the respondents is very low, NGOs must take up literacy awareness campaign programmes so that workers can be made aware of their rights and

- can use the same for getting better job opportunities in towns and cities.
4. Looking at the poor living standards and hygiene standards state government should delegate the responsibility to Block Development Officer and Village Sarpanch to provide services such as clean drinking water, proper housing, electricity, housing, proper toilets etc to uplift their standards. The concerned public authorities should be held accountable to this.
 5. In order to ensure that production does not get disrupted, initiatives should be taken to build pucca roads so that raw materials reach the workshops in time, electricity supply should be regularized, and adequate supply of raw materials, tools and equipment should be provided frequently.
 6. To ensure that these workers are able to sell their products at remunerative prices, their holding capacity and distribution channels should be improved with government directing gram panchayats and block development officers to take up the responsibility of improving godowns, warehousing facilities, transport facilities etc.
 7. Cooperative credit societies and cooperative marketing societies should join hands together to provide credit to these people on easy terms and help them in selling the produce in markets at good prices. This would go a long way to prevent these poor people from getting into the clutches of moneylenders and exploitation.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the present study that workers engaged in different occupation in Kalichabad have been facing lots of problems in modern period. Low income, poor infrastructure, pathetic living standards, day to day problem in production and distribution process is prevalent which really needs to be addressed as soon as possible. The socio-economic conditions of the workers despite tall claims of successive governments remains below the mark in modern times. Because of poor literacy rate people don't have proper knowledge and awareness about hygiene, sanitation and healthy work conditions at home as well as at workplace. Its high time that both government as well as non-government agencies take up the challenge of eliminating these issues by working together in close coordination.

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